

Effective Psychotherapy: concepts, strategies, practices. Presentation of psychotherapy based on Paul Diel's theory (Psychology of motivation)

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Abstract: This lecture will hold three parts: 1. Show that the theory of Paul Diel is in the continuity of the philosophical and later psychological discoveries. Define the frame of the interventions of this method. Position of the patient, state of the patient, duration of the analysis, medical collaboration. 2. Show that this theory is based on the laws of internal world, which allow to understand what takes place at the psychic level. Three major classes of psychic deviations can be explained by the theory of Psychology of Motivation. 3. Description of cases: two cases of psychotherapy will be presented in order to illustrate the method and its results.

Keywords: psychotherapy, psychology of motivation, Paul Diel's theory

Part I

Paul Diel belongs to the greater thinkers of the modern world, without having had recognition in his lifetime. His work is based on discoveries made earlier, from philosophers to psychologists. This continuity is already a proof of a scientific method which can include all the major steps in the research about the way human brain is working.

The aim of psychology is to study « how does our brain work? ». Can we predict what is going to happen if we think this or that way? Prediction and verification are the principles used in physics or chemistry, which give us confidence in these sciences. But to

understand, predict and verify doesn't automatically offer a solution to the patient. Why? Just because if a patient doesn't want to recover, nobody can force him or her to. We have to admit that sometimes patients prefer their illness rather than a recovery, because psychiatric disease involves the patient himself. To get the patient out of his illness we need to offer him or her a better choice in terms of satisfaction. It is up to him or her, after the proposal is made, to accept it or not. Suffering may be pleasant when everybody takes care of you. To quit this sort of satisfaction demands quite a strong willingness. Paul Diel and all others

researchers have understood this problem. This is the limit of all therapeutic practices.

A therapy can only operate if the patient wants to. If so, then the therapist needs to explain him or her how a brain works, including the patient's own brain. The patient has to be involved and ready to make some experiments on himself or herself, because this is the only way to feel a different kind of satisfaction and to be able to change his usual way of thinking towards the one proposed to him or her by the therapy.

In the “dielienne therapy” the patient has to listen to the therapist and to write down explanations made, in order to learn and then to be able to redo the thinking. The therapist has to understand the case and formulate a solution through a thinking. This is how “dielienne therapy” proceeds. For sure it means a lot of work both for patient and therapist. But it is so interesting and so moving! For sure when the therapist succeeds to cure the patient from such an disease, it is a

wonderful shock!

The duration of the therapy is about 1 to 10 working sessions. In some cases, it is even possible to achieve the cure with a single session. Why is this possible ? Just because in some rare cases, the understanding of the causes of the disease is enough to free the patient from his symptoms. Five to seven sessions is more usual, depending of the way the therapist can address the problem and expose the patient's way of thinking. A therapy can be pursued during a lifetime if the patient, after having recovered, is interested in the method as such and wants to help others.

Medical collaboration is needed to help the patient equilibrate his or her production of hormones (serotonin, dopamine, norepinephrine or others) disrupted by his or her noxious habit of daydreaming. Only a joined action of psychiatrist and therapist may provide a solution. Tablets are a great help but can't rebuild the patient's way of thinking. This has to be made by a therapist.

Part II

Paul Diel's advanced psychological theory based on methodical introspection uses a glossary of around one hundred terms, relative to specific concepts of the internal world. As these concepts can be related with each other, laws can be established. Even if a precise means of quantification has not yet been found, neurosciences already provide some clues to find a way of measuring the psychological activity of human brain. A suggestion or a daydream instantaneously leads to a production of hormones which can

be measured. Experiments can confirm these laws and may validate the theory. Let us present at least the very first law expressed in Diel's theory, “ $E=I$ ”, meaning that the degree of exaltation equals the degree of inhibition. If you get overexcited, thus experimenting an exaltation caused by an idea, then you will create an internal inhibition of the same intensity, or vice-versa. This may seem obvious or completely irrational, but experimentation demonstrates that this law works and is applicable. When such exaltation arises, an energy is

blocked due to the fact that exaltation creates inhibition and both are ambivalent. This internal contradiction blocks the energy necessary to perform any action related to this exaltation. Understanding the relationship between E and I allows the patient to release energy. This can be intimately felt.

Paul Diel has discovered around twenty laws which rule our way of thinking and, thus, our decisions. These laws allow us to explain what is going on in our mental state and, more than that, can predict what is going to happen if we maintain a given way of thinking. Admittedly, the formula presented by the author are still under study and have submitted to further experimentations. Nevertheless, the results already obtained by therapy confirm that this is the direction to be followed.

Each of us have a secret goal to reach, a kind of absolute, which is never allowed go public but which does exist as a task to be accomplished during our life. This is what Diel expresses as overexalted task (*tâche exaltée* in French). This Task can be unrealistic and very often is. There are three different noxious ways to deal with it, potentially leading to mental disorder. Either by denying it to be present in

our mind, or by admitting it but without identifying it to be unrealistic and unattainable.

Denying that the overexalted task is present in our mind, can lead to mental disorder, and as a result the body will produce symptoms such as addictions, OCD (obsessional-compulsive disorder) or any other type of obsessions. The cause of this mechanism lies in the unrealistic nature of the overexalted task, leading to permanent dissatisfaction, which has to express itself through symptoms because of the energy blocked by the internal conflict. If the overexalted task is concentrated into a unique goal (for example, the dream of being a genius) then the patient will be alternatively in a state of euphoria and abulia -that is to say psychasthenia. If the overexalted task is disseminated, fractioned into multiple small tasks (for example, the need to take care perfectly of the household chores, and to be professionally perfect, and so on), the patient will be in a permanent state of dispersion of energy and urge to please others: hysterical (histrion) personality.

These are the three main types of psychic illness (neurosis) according to Diel's theory. All combinations can occur from these three major types.

Part III

The two cases described hereafter refer to patients who were under medical treatment prescribed by psychiatrists. As a result of Dielian therapy, both patients recovered rapidly from their mental disease and were able to reduce the dose of their

medications. The therapeutic work continued after this first stage of recovery, but the sessions were more and more sporadic.

1. First case. A married woman who has been in burn out in her

professional situation and was involved in familial conflict.

Medicine: Zoloft (ISRS) 2 pills / day, Strezam (anxiolytic) 2p / morning and evening

Problem: overloaded at work and unable to say no. No feeling of happiness.

The patient was depreciating herself in a drastic way. She was feeling hopeless, usefulness, idiot... Therapy explained her that by ambivalence, (law of ambivalence), she was unconsciously dreaming that she was above everyone. This process was blocking all her energy. Therapy was able to deconstruct the process of self-justification she put in place, thanks to application of the laws expressed in Diel's theory.

Result: after 5 therapeutic sessions, no more medicine, able to manage her situation at home as well as at work. Needs some more sessions to maintain this situation (every 3 months two to three sessions). Only Strezam remaining 1p in the morning.

2. Married woman who wanted to be perfect in her job, has great

difficulties at home and has suffered from a burn out.

Medicine: Citaloprane 30mg (ISRS)/ day

Problem: wants to prove that everything she does is perfect.

Therapy explains that perfection is not reachable. The major point in the explanation was to connect the different (four) types of self-justification she was giving to herself to prove that perfection was the only way to do her job. These self-justifications lead to a burn out automatically.

Therapy also demonstrates her that familial and professional problems are linked together.

These demonstrations are based on the analysis of her speech, detecting illogisms and explaining why and how her overexalted task was impossible to accomplish. This impossibility being the root of her problems.

Result: after 2 months and 8 therapeutic sessions: Feels better, is able to manage her job with less stress, no more burn out, Citaloprane 5 mg (ISRS)/ day. Keeps on the sessions once a week (duration could be a year to get rid of every trouble).

Conclusion

Only a strong collaboration between sciences of internal world and external world such as medicine may bring a solution to solve the psychiatric diseases. We need to set up a strong collaboration between psychiatry and psychology to help patients.

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